

Cerebrospinal Fluid Study in a Tertiary Care Hospital**Balram Kanwar¹, Amit Agravat², Gauravi Dhruva³, Krupal Pujara⁴**¹2nd Year Resident, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India²Professor, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India³Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Krupal Pujara

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Abstract:

Introduction: An infection of the meninges that encircle the brain and spinal cord is known as meningitis. Usually, bacterial, viral, or fungal infections are seen. One of the most dangerous illnesses that affect people of all ages like bacterial, viral, or fungal meningitis is linked to both immediate consequences and long-term morbidity.

Aim and Objective: The present study was undertaken to analyze Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) parameters and to determine the type of meningitis infection, which will guide the physician to treat various type of meningitis accordingly.

Materials and Methods: This was a cross-sectional study conducted over June 2023 to November 2023 in Department of Pathology at P.D.U. Medical College and Hospital in Rajkot, Gujarat, India. Study participants included 478 cerebrospinal fluid samples from clinically suspected meningitis cases across all age groups admitted to the hospital on CSF Chemical examination and microscopic examination was done.

Results: Out of total 478 cases majority of the patients between 19-60 years and slight male predominance was seen. Examination of Cerebrospinal Fluid sample showed that 60.25% were turbid and 38.91% were clear. Total White blood cell count 1-200 cells/cu mm were seen in majority of cases. Protein levels >50 mg/dl were seen in 32% of cases, glucose level <45mg/dl were seen in 28% cases. Diagnosis of study subjects showed that majority 66.94% were normal, 16.31 % had viral meningitis, 8.31% had bacterial meningitis and 7.32 % had tubercular meningitis.

Conclusion: Meningitis remains a major health care problem with incidence rising in adults and children. An early pathological analysis and providing appropriate antibiotic therapy are life-saving and they also reduce morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: CSF, Viral meningitis.

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Introduction

An infection of the meninges that encircle the brain and spinal cord is known as meningitis. Usually, bacterial, viral, or fungal infections are seen. One of the most dangerous illnesses that affect people of all ages, bacterial, viral, or fungal meningitis is linked to both immediate consequences and long-term morbidity.

The etiology of bacterial meningitis differs depending on the age group and global location. The most frequently identified organisms linked to bacterial meningitis are *Escherichia coli*, *Neisseria Meningitidis*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and *Hemophilus influenzae*.

Meningitis is difficult to diagnose clinically since its early symptoms are frequently nonspecific, especially in infants and toddlers because of the immaturity of their central nervous systems. For an

early diagnosis to be achieved, laboratory support is therefore essential. The basis for routine CSF analysis is protein and glucose biochemistry analysis, as well as macroscopic evaluation of the CSF and microscopic inspection for pathogenic cells. The traditional CSF abnormalities associated with bacterial meningitis include increased protein concentration, decreased glucose concentration, and polymorphonuclear leukocytosis.

The most effective diagnostic technique is CSF culture, which is positive in most cases. Appropriate treatment requires prompt assessment for antibiotic sensitivity. A etiological diagnosis mostly relies on CSF analysis and culture because clinical presentation is imprecise.

The present study was undertaken to analyze CSF parameters and to determine the type of meningitis

infection, which will guide the local clinician to treat accordingly.

Materials and Methods

This was a cross-sectional study conducted from June 2023 to November 2023 for period of six months in Central Clinical Laboratory, Department of Pathology, P.D.U. Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, Gujarat, India. Study participants included 478 CSF samples from clinically suspected meningitis cases across all age groups who were admitted to the clinical wards of P.D.U. Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, Gujarat, India.

Patients who experienced head trauma, underwent neurosurgical procedures, had tuberculosis, anaerobic fermentation, viral, fungal, or parasite causes, or who had taken antibiotics within a week of their hospital visit were not included in the study.

Sample collection and processing: The laboratory processed CSF samples as soon as they were brought in sterile containers. Three test tubes were

filled with an aliquot of CSF. The first test tube's sample was utilized to analyze the cell type and total white blood cell count.

The second test tube's sample was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 2000 rpm to minimize contamination. The sediment was then utilized to inoculate the culture media before Gram's stain was applied directly to create a smear. For the examination of glucose and proteins, a third test tube was employed.

CSF investigation: Examination The volume, turbidity, purulence, and blood staining of the CSF were noted. Microscopic analysis had leucocytes counted and CSF was added to the counting into the improved Neubauer chamber to complete the cell count and cell type. A centrifuged deposit film was analyzed to determine the main cell type and to perform a differential count. Using the Roche/Hitachi Cobas 311 system with calibrators and internal controls supplied by Roche and in accordance with manufacturer's instructions, protein and glucose levels were determined by immune turbidometry assay.

Table 1: Distribution of Patients as per Age.

Age in years	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<1 years	153	32%
1-5 years	102	21%
6-18 years	41	9%
19-60 years	164	34%
>60 years	18	4%
Total	478	100%

Results: In present study, out of total 478 cases, patients aged less than one year and between 19-60 years samples were noted maximum amongst all age groups.

Table 2: Distribution of Patients as per Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	278	58%
Female	200	42%
Total	478	100%

Table no 2 shows sex wise distribution of total 478 cases in which males were found more than females respectively.

Figure 1:

Graph 1 showed that majority of Cerebrospinal fluid sample were send from Pediatrics Intensive Care unit (PICU) (44.8%), followed by Medicine ward (30.1%), Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) (16.7%) and Emergency ward (6.3%) respectively.

Table 3: Color of Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) sample

Color	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Colorless	354	74.06%
Slight yellowish	22	4.6%
Reddish	24	5.02%
Whitish	78	16.31%
Total	478	100%

Table 3 shows color of Cerebrospinal Fluid samples; majority of the sample 74.06% were colourless, 16.31% were whitish, 5.02% were reddish, 4.6% were slight yellowish.

Table 4: Total Leukocyte count (TLC) in microscopic examination

TLC (CELLS /CUMM)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<10	126	26.36%
1-200	328	68.61%
>200	24	5.18%
Total	478	100%

Table no 4 shows total leukocyte count in microscopic examination in which majority of the subjects shows TLC between 1-200 while only 24 cases show TLC > 200 %.

Table 5: Protein and Glucose parameters in study subjects

Protein (mg/dl)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<50	325	68%
>50	153	32%
Glucose (mg/dl)		
<45	134	28%
>45	344	72%

Table no 5 shows protein and glucose parameter of study subjects, in which total 60% had glucose Value < 50 mg/dl.

Table 6: CSF analysis in various type of meningitis

CSF analysis	Viral	Bacterial	Tuberculosis
Pressure	Increased	Increased	Non-elevated
Color	Turbid	Turbid	Clear
Glucose	<40 mg5	Low	Normal to mild less
Proteins	Elevated	Greatly elevated	Normal to mild elevated
WBCs	10-2000/cu mm	Elevated but <500	>100/cumm
WBC types	Neutrophils	Lymphocytes	Lymphocytes
No. of cases in our study	78	45	35

Table 6: Diagnosis of study subjects

Diagnosis	Freq.	Percentage (%)
Normal	320	66.94%
Bacterial meningitis	45	8.41%
Viral meningitis	78	16.31%
Tubercular meningitis	35	7.32%
Total	478	100%

Table 6 shows the diagnosis of study subjects; majority 66.94 % was normal, 16.31 % had Viral Meningitis, 8.41 % had Bacterial Meningitis and 7.32 % had Tubercular Meningitis.

Discussion

The present study was undertaken to analyze Cerebrospinal fluid parameters and] to determine the type of meningitis infection in department of Pathology at P.D.U. Medical College and Hospital in Rajkot, Gujarat.

In present study among study subjects around one-third was <1 year of age followed by 1-5 years of age, and one-third were 19-60 years. Male were slightly more than female. Raj KA et al in a similar study reported that Infants constituted 20% and the children above 6 years constituted 60%. Male children predominated in the study population. In a study by Garg et al. conducted in children from 1 month to 5 years age group in Shimla, India in 2013, 57 cases were diagnosed as ABM, cases in the age group of 3–12 months constituted 59.6%. They reported male to female ratio of 2:1. Karanika et al. studied children with meningitis from 1 month to 14 years age group in South Africa and reported the mean age of patients as 2.6 years. Predominance with a male: female ratio of 1.3:1 was reported by them.

In present study, highest percentage of bacterial meningitis cases was observed in the age group of 1months to 2 years. This can be attributed to decreased immunity and high vascularity of the brain in children less than 2 years of age. The increased risk of bacterial meningitis in elderly is multifactorial and includes both a greater propensity for underlying acute and chronic diseases like pneumonia, diabetes, renal or hepatic

failure. In present study the color of Cerebrospinal fluid samples showed that majority of the sample were colourless and some were whitish and reddish. Whereas the appearance of Cerebrospinal fluid sample showed that majority were turbid and rest were clear. Ramesh S.T. et al study the Pathological and Microbiological Analysis of Cerebrospinal Fluid in Bacterial Meningitis and reported that Macroscopic appearance of Cerebrospinal fluid, in 25% cases shows turbid fluid and 5% cases hemorrhagic appearance [11]. Normal Cerebrospinal fluid is usually clear and colourless like water. Cerebrospinal fluid turbidity may be caused by increased cell count (WBC leucocytes, erythrocytes, bacteria, fungi and parasites). When blood is present in a CSF specimen, it is necessary to determine whether it is due to a traumatic Lumbar Puncture or intracranial bleeding [12].

In present study the Cerebrospinal fluid parameters among study subjects showed that total white blood cell count 10-20 cells/cu mm were seen in majority of the cases, Protein levels >50 mg/dl were seen in one third of cases. Ramesh S.T. et al in a similar study reported that Total white blood cell count >1000cells /ul were seen in 20% of cases and neutrophils predominance were seen in 30% cases which were also observed by Reyes et al, Dunbar SA et al and Fouad R et al study

Lymphocytes and monocytes with occasionally ependymal cells are found in normal Cerebrospinal fluid. An increased number of neutrophilic granulocytes can be found in bacterial and acute viral Central Nervous System infections. In bacterial meningitis cases, Cerebrospinal fluid shows rise in total white blood cell count with increase in neutrophil counts. Ramesh S.T. et al

reported that Cerebrospinal fluid protein level >50mg/dl with glucose level <45mg/dl were seen in bacterial meningitis. As glucose is actively transported across the blood brain barrier the Cerebrospinal fluid glucose levels are directly proportionate to the plasma levels.

Elevated Cerebrospinal fluid protein concentration can be found in the majority of patients with Bacterial, Cryptococcal and Tubercular meningitis. Coexistent findings of low sugar level and marked elevation in Cerebrospinal fluid protein level help distinguish patients with bacterial meningitis from those with viral disease.

Conclusion

Meningitis remains a major health care problem with incidence rising in adults and children. An early pathological analysis and providing appropriate antibiotic therapy are lifesaving and they also reduce morbidity and mortality. Majority had Viral Meningitis followed by Bacterial Meningitis and Tubercular Meningitis.

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